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***In silico* Molecular docking studies of Ferulic acid against HIV-1 target enzymes**

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ABSTRACT

The acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS), a disorder in which a person's immune system starts to deteriorate and leads to life-threatening infections, is brought on by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), a lentivirus (a type of retrovirus). There are two types of HIV, the first of which is very contagious. As a result, to cure the HIV, the molecular docking technique was employed. PDB crystal structures of the HIV-1 reverse transcriptase, HIV-1 integrase, and HIV-1 protease enzyme along with the ligand Ferulic acid, were used for docking. Molecular docking was carried out using Autodock. When compared to other HIV-1 target enzymes and to the conventional HIV-1 RT inhibitor, ferulic acid has the lowest docking score (-6.29 Kcal/mol). The HIV RT's contact residues are LYS103, GLY99, VAL179, TYR188, LYS101, LEU100, TYR318, VAL106, PRO236, HIS235, LEU234, and PHE227. The discovery of this hit molecule, which was intended to be a novel potential anti-HIV-1 inhibitor, may aid in the development of new HIV-1 RTs. As a result, *in silico* analysis increases the potential for therapeutic development. Additionally, experimental testing must be carried out to verify Ferulic acid's efficacy.

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KEYWORDS:
Docking, Ferulic acid, HIV-1, PDB, Autodock, AIDS, HIV-1 RT

Introduction

Acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS), one of the most contagious diseases on the world, is brought on by the human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). There is currently no effective drug or vaccination that can totally treat AIDS. Currently, there are two known types of HIV (HIV-1 and HIV-2) (Gupta et al, 2016). HIV-2 has a limited rate of transmission, whereas HIV-1 is highly prevalent worldwide (Gallo, 2002; Sanjuan et al, 2011). A retrovirus called HIV-1 has three essential enzymes to lengthen its life cycle: (1) Reverse-e transcriptase (RT), which is made up of a 66 kDa (p66) and a 51 kDa (p51) component, is produced when the Gag-Pol polyprotein precursor is split in two by the viral protease. P51 and p66 share the same first 440

residues. These residues contain the polymerase subdomains thumb, palm, fingers, and connection in both subunits (Kohlstaedt et al, 1992). (2) HIV Protease (PR), which is required for the processing of new pathogenic viral particles; (3) Integrase (IN), which is in charge of facilitating the viral DNA's 3-preprocessing and insertion into the host DNA; and (Weissbrich et al, 2022; Luthra et al, 2017). This enzyme causes viral polyproteins, which are crucial for digesting proteins, to become active (Luo et al, 2013; Gujjeti, Rajendra Prasad et al, 2014). In order to explore molecular docking with chosen molecule ferulic acid, these three enzymes were chosen.

The phenolic acid family, which ferulic acid ([E]-3-[4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-phenyl] prop-2-enoic acid) belongs to, is frequently present in

plant tissues (Mattila et al, 2022). Secondary metabolites known as phenolic acids come in a variety of chemical and biological forms. The majority of the plants are found bound, as ester or glycosides, lignin components, and hydrolysis tannins (Parus et al, 2013). Whole grains, spinach, parsley, grapes, rhubarb, and cereal seeds, primarily those from wheat, oats, rye, and barley, are the foods that contain ferulic acid most frequently. The antioxidant activity of phenolic acids, especially those derived from cinnamic acid, is one of its most significant functions. This activity is principally influenced by the number of hydroxyl and methoxy groups connected to the phenyl ring (Aguilar et al, 2017; Bezerra et al, 2017). Compared to other phenolic acids, ferulic acid is more readily absorbed by the body and stays in the blood longer. It is believed that ferulic acid is a superior antioxidant (Teengam et al, 2013). Ferulic acid has a low toxicity and a wide range of physiological effects, such as anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticancer (against lung, breast, colon, and skin cancer), anti-arrhythmic, and antithrombotic activity. It has also shown to have anti-diabetic and immunostimulant effects. It also lessens nerve cell damage and may aid in the repair of damaged cells (Moldovan et al, 2017).

Recent bioinformatics research using the molecular docking technique has accurately analysed the mechanism of HIV-1 activity inhibition (Mukesh and Rakesh, 2011; Grinter et al, 2014). Molecular Docking has a unique role in the development of novel medications and the assessment of their efficacy (Luscombe et al, 2011; MamidalaEstari et al, 2021). In order to create pharmaceuticals with the fewest adverse effects possible, it is possible to find inhibitors of this enzyme among natural chemicals, leading to the discovery of one of the novel treatments for HIV-1 infection. This ferulic acid has not been researched for its antiviral action, particularly its anti-HIV activity. Therefore, the goal of this research is to examine how ferulic acid interacts with HIV-1 target enzymes during molecular docking.

Material and Methods

Protein Retrieval

The 3D structures of HIV-1 Integrase, HIV-1 RT, and HIV-1 protease served as the foundation for this investigation. The RSCB protein data bank (<http://www.rcsb.org/>) was utilised to retrieve the 3D structures of HIV-1 reverse transcriptase (PDB: 1REV), HIV-1 integrase (PDB: 1BL3), and HIV-1 protease (PDB: 1HPV), which were used as a receptor of the experimental object (Figure-1). The resolutions for the HIV-1 RT, integrase, and protease enzyme structures with the PDB codes 1REV, 1BL3, and 1HPV were 2.6Å, 2.00Å, and 1.90Å, respectively.

All water molecules were eliminated prior to analysis, and ADT software was used to create the necessary files for AutoDock by assigning hydrogen polarities, figuring Gasteiger charges for protein structures, and converting protein structures from the.PDB file format to.PDBQT format.

Preparation of ligand structure for ferulic acid

The National Center for Biotechnology Information's PubChem Compound Database was used to retrieve the structure of ferulic acid in the Spatial Data File (.SDF) file format. Structure of ferulic acid was downloaded in the Spatial Data File (.SDF) file format from the PubChem Compound Database (National Center for Biotechnology Information; <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>)(Figure-2.).

Figure-2. 3D structure of Ferulic Acid
(Retrieved from
<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>).

AutoDock programmes are included in the AutoDock bundle. The energy grid maps are computed by the AutoGrid programme. For LGA

The SDF format of chemical structures was converted utilising Discovery Studio Biovia 2017 and to the PDB format. The investigation of ligand structures using non-polar hydrogen combinations, Gasteiger charge additions, and rotatable bonds was done next using ADT for components of the ligand. Then, the ligand was converted from PDB format. ADT-based PDBQT format allows for usage with AutoDock4 (AD4).

Molecular Docking Experiment Settings:

The ready proteins and ligand structures were saved in the PDBQT file format for molecular docking experiments. As a tool for molecular graphical visualisation, AutoDockTools (ADT) was employed. Both the AutoGrid and

algorithms, the initial population was set to 50 people, the number of energy function evaluations was set to 2.5×10^5 , and the maximum number of generations was set at 27,000. The AutoDock software is employed for the conformation search and energy evaluation.

Results and Discussion

It has been challenging to find an HIV cure for many years. Numerous chemicals have been researched against certain viral components to inhibit the virus from propagating in the host. It is exciting to consider employing a recognized phytochemical to create a disease treatment (Akbar et al, 2011). The viral protease, reverse transcriptase, and integrase enzymes are those that the virus encodes. Targeting HIV integrase

Table-1. Molecular docking analysis of Ferulic acid against HIV-1 RT, HIV-1 integrase and HIV-1 protease

Selected Ligand	HIV-1 target enzymes	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	Residues involving interaction	No. of H bonds	Interaction of residues forming H bonds
Ferulic-Acid	HIV-1 RT	-6.29	GLY99, VAL179, TYR188, LYS101, LEU100, TYR318, VAL106, PRO236, HIS235, LEU234, PHE227	1	LYS:103
	HIV-1 Integrase	-5.19	GLY:82, MET:154, VAL:77, ILE:151, SER:81, ALA:80, VAL:79,	2	GLN:62, ARG:199
	HIV-1 protease	-1.28	GLY:27, ASP:25, ALA:28, VAL:82, ILE:84, ILE:47, THR:80, ILE :54	1	THR :80

Table-2. Binding energy of test compounds and reference drugs with HIV-1 target enzymes

S.No	HIV-1 Target Enzymes	Ferulic Acid	Binding energy of Reference Drugs in Kcal/Mol		
			Elvitegravir (HIV-1 integrase inhibitor)	Doxorubicin (HIV-1 RT inhibitor)	Amprenavir (HIV-1 Protease Inhibitor)
1	HIV-1 RT	-6.29	-	-4.91	-
2	HIV-1 Integrase	-5.19	-4.78	-	-
3	HIV-1 Protease	-1.28	-	-	-2.4

makes sense in the fight against HIV infection and AIDS. The 32-kDa HIV integrase (IN) enzyme is produced by the virus's pol gene (Maroun et al, 1999). From the RCSB PDB data repository, the 3D structure of the HIV-1 Integrase Protein was downloaded in PDB format. This protein is necessary for viral replication and integration of the viral DNA into the host. In this study, we used computational docking methods to determine how ferulic acid binds to the enzyme.

Molecular Docking Analysis

One of the most effective and widely used structure-based *in silico* strategies for predicting the interactions between molecules and their biological targets is molecular docking. Typically, it involves first predicting the molecular orientation of a ligand within a receptor and then estimating their complementarity by applying a scoring function (Segall et al, 2014; Davella et al, 2021; Kitchen et al, 2004). It helps the drug researcher move forward with evaluating the most promising drug

candidate by choosing the optimal protein-ligand pair based on their affinity for binding. different place of protein for docking and ΔG is

In order to molecularly dock with the HIV integrase, HIV-1 RT, and HIV-1 protease enzymes, ferulic acid was utilised. Ferulic acid's binding energy values are shown in Table-1, and their values show that they have a good affinity for the target enzymes. While (Table-2) compares the binding energy values of various standard drugs used to treat HIV with ferulic acid.

Docking energies of HIV-1 RT, PR and Integrase with ferulic acid ligand are shown in Table-1 and Table-2. In this table, the number of score is

free energy of docking.

Figure-3 depicts the docking of ferulic acid with HIV-1 integrase. With a binding energy of -5.19 Kcal/mol, the interaction of the ferulic acid's oxygen forms two H-bonds to the residues GLN:62 and ARG:199, and one H-bond to the residue ALA80 (Figure-3). Additionally, ferulic acid interacts hydrophobically with residues GLY:82, MET:154, VAL:77, ILE:151, SER;81, ALA:80, and VAL:79.

Figure-4 displays the results of the docking of ferulic acid with HIV-1 protease. Ferulic acid

interacts with oxygen to generate two H-bonds to residues ALA:28 and THR:80, and with hydrogen to form one H-bond to residue ASP:25 and one H-bond to residue THR:80 once more, all with a 1.8\AA distance. Additionally, ferulic acid interacts hydrophobically with the residues of GLY:27, ASP:25, ALA:28, VAL:82, ILE:84, ILE:47, THR:80, and ILE:54.

Using autodock, docking simulations of the ligand ferulic acid with HIV-1 RT revealed that ferulic acid had a binding score of -6.29 kcal/mol in the lowest conformation, compared to -5.19 and -1.28 kcal/mol for ferulic acid with HIV-1 integrase and HIV-1 protease,

respectively (Table-2). These findings suggest that, when compared to the reference drugs, which showed binding energy of -4.91 Kcal/mol, Ferulic Acid exhibits the highest binding affinity for HIV-1 RT. When compared to their reference medicines, the binding energies with the other two enzymes are quite effective, with the exception of ferulic acid docking against HIV-1 protease.

The results of the docking demonstrate that the ferulic acid ligand forms only one hydrogen bond with the Lys103 residue of the HIV-1 RT (Figure-5). Ferulic acid ligand and HIV-1 integrase have two hydrogen bond contacts with Gln62 and Arg199 residues, but ferulic acid

ligand and HIV-1 protease only have one hydrogen bond interaction with Thr80 residue. There are 11 hydrophobic contacts between the HIV-1 RT protein and the ferulic acid ligand, involving the residues Gly99, Val179, Tyr188, Lys101, Tyr 318, Val106, Pro236 and Phe227.

Conclusion

Despite the existence of medications that can be used to manage HIV infection and even lessen viral transmission, HIV continues to be a leading cause of death and a threat to the health of millions of people worldwide. For the purpose of finding brand-new inhibitors for the

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure. Molecular Docking Studies of HIV-1 Protease with Ferulic Acid.

- (A) Surface representation of ferulic acid binding in the pocket of HIV-1 RT;
 (B) A 3D representation of ferulic acid interactions with HIV-1 RT
 (C) A 2D representation of Ferulic acid interactions with HIV-1 RT (Green colour lines shows hydrogen bond interactions)

HIV-1 RT, HIV-1 integrase, and HIV-1 protease

enzymes, bioactive compounds were screened *in silico*. The time needed to produce new medications is shortened by these examinations. The importance of *in silico* screening of ferulic acid and its success in discovering HIV inhibitors that are effective against the aforementioned three HIV-1 target enzymes are highlighted by the current work. According to the results of this study, ferulic acid is an effective therapeutic molecule against HIV sickness that is similar to doxorubicin. We anticipate that the results of these experiments will help in the development of new and potent HIV drugs. Future research will therefore need to validate this ligand both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Conflict of Interest

Authors do not have any possible conflicts of interest.

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